

Personal social networks and individual voting turnout in a comparative perspective

Oana Lup¹

Abstract

I use survey data collected in a comparative, cross-country study (Comparative National Election Project) to analyze the relationships between people's embeddedness in either strong or weak social networks and their likelihood to participate in elections in countries with different length of democratic experiences. Results indicate that exclusive exposure to similar political views either in strong or weak social networks increases the likelihood of voting, while exposure to a mix of similar and dissimilar political views has a mobilizing role when occurring in weak networks, in countries with a longer democratic past.

Keywords

social networks; political discussion; voting behavior; comparative research; old and new democracies

¹ Oana Lup (ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8003-3897>) received her PhD in Political Science from Central European University, Budapest and is currently teaching in the Department of Social Work, Journalism, Public Relations, and Sociology of "Lucian Blaga" University of Sibiu. Prior to this she worked at Central European University and University of Mannheim. Her research interests include public opinion and electoral behavior, civic engagement, deliberative democracy, stereotypes, and prejudices.

Introduction

Do personal social networks affect people's decisions to participate in elections? In spite of mounting empirical evidence supporting an affirmative answer to this question, little is yet known about the contextual character of this influence (Schmitt-Beck and Lup 2013), especially, outside the "WEIRD (Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, and Democratic)" context (although see Eveland, Song, and Beck 2015). Are all types of social networks equally influential in general, or their effect is a function of macro-contextual features?

In this study I examine the role played by the democratic experience of countries in shaping the relationship between people's embeddedness in social networks and their decision to cast a vote in elections. In particular, I explore whether this relationship varies as a function of the length of democratic culture of countries.

Empirical evidence about the role played by personal social networks in electoral mobilization comes predominantly from single country studies and oftentimes from established democracies. In countries with a recent democratic past though, interpersonal trust appears to be low, thus casting a shade of doubt with regard to the efficacy of social networks in voting mobilization. This is due to the fact that citizens of former authoritarian regimes have experienced to date different patterns of social and political interaction compared to their counterparts from countries with longer democratic experience. Specifically, they appear to be part of less extensive social networks, less likely to engage in casual political communication with their peers, and less likely to be exposed to political disagreement in casual conversations (Iglic 2003; Iglic and Font Fábregas 2007; Richardson and Beck 2007; Beck and Gunther 2010; Lup 2015).

This paper investigates whether and how such differences in their micro-social environments and habits of informal political conversations affect the social calculus of voting. To address these questions I conduct a comparative, cross-country analysis of the relationship between various features of two types of personal social networks and individual voting behavior. The two types of networks are referred to as strong and weak social networks (Granovetter 1973). Strong networks comprise close, intimate, trustful relationships that develop among people who interact often, while weak social networks include social interactions that come about as a result of people's social roles, for example those defined by workplaces and neighborhoods. The analysis draws on survey data collected in a comparative, cross-country project, the Comparative National Elections Project (CNEP).

Results of my analysis indicate that exclusive exposure to similar political views in either strong or weak social networks is positively related to an increase in the likelihood of individual turnout. Exposure to a mix of similar and dissimilar political views in strong networks appears to be positively linked to an increase in the likelihood of electoral participation, but only in countries with longer democratic experience. Drawing on social psychology theories suggesting that people feel more confident to reveal their political preferences to members of strong social networks rather than to those of weak ones, I interpret this latter finding as evidence that strong, intimate social networks are better loci for engaging in genuine political debates that in turn results in increased political engagement. Nevertheless, this holds only in countries with longer democratic experience, whose citizens are more accustomed to the exercise of deliberation and do not fear the disruptive potential of engaging in debates with fellow citizens.

Social networks and individual voting turnout: state of the art

The mobilizing effect of personal social networks has been shown to be a function of both structural and content-based features of these social interactions. A few of these features have been consistently

found to be related to an increase in electoral participation, while the effect of others appeared to be less coherent across studies. The former includes the size of political discussion networks, the frequency of political conversations carried out in these settings, and exposure to similar political views in social networks, while the latter features exposure to political disagreement in political discussion networks.

With regard to the size of social networks and the frequency of political encounters within them, a robust finding of extant research is that increased exposure to political conversations, either due to large networks of political discussants or to high frequency of political encounters is related to an increase in individual turnout (Knoke 1990; Mutz 2002b; Nir 2005; Pattie and Johnston 2009, but see Leighley 1990 for a contradicting result, i.e. size of political discussion network being negatively related with individual turnout). Regarding exposure to similar political views, agreeable political conversations and embeddedness in political discussion networks in which most people share similar political views and partisan preferences have been shown to be particularly conducive to electoral mobilization (Mutz 2002a, 2006; Morales 2010; Klofstad 2011; Nir 2011). Such instances of what some authors have labeled “safe discussion” (Eveland and Hively 2009) and others “supportive networks” (Nir 2011) stirs the participative ethos by ensuring people about the righteous character of their political views and strengthening their political identity (Mutz 2006).

As mentioned above, less consistent results are found in extant literature with regard to effects of exposure to political disagreement in conversations with peers. Some studies suggest that this might be due to the use of different operationalizations of this concept across studies, which are informed by distinct theoretical arguments with regard to the way exposure to political views that contradicts one’s own affects individual electoral behavior. This inconsistent usage of the concept of political disagreement and the ensuing incoherence in the measures employed across various studies make the comparison of extant findings quite challenging (Eveland and Hively 2009).

Originally understood as an ideological imbalance resulting from membership in social groups that embodied conflicting political views (e.g. the Catholic businessman), political disagreement or “cross-pressure” was shown to be related to a delay in the formation of voting preferences in elections and to increased chances of electoral abstention (Lazarsfeld, Berelson, and Gaudet 1944; Berelson, Lazarsfeld, and McPhee 1954). Unstable voters and defectors were shown to come mainly from the group of those who either could not recall any political discussion in their groups or were exposed to conflicting political views (Lazarsfeld, Berelson, and Gaudet 1944; Berelson, Lazarsfeld, and McPhee 1954). In later research, especially influenced by network analysis paradigm of studies, political disagreement was measured directly, either by asking respondents about their perception on the agreeable/disagreeable nature of their political encounters with peers, or by drawing on and matching respondents’ reports in surveys on their political preferences and their perceptions of discussants’ political views. This represented a ‘huge operational leap from knowing that a person is both Catholic and a businessman, for example, to infer that they are subject to political cross-pressures from pro-Democratic Catholic acquaintances and pro-Republican business people.’ (Mutz 2002b: 842). Inconsistencies persisted, though, seeing as the concept of political disagreement has been indistinctly applied to two different situations, namely what Eveland and Hively call “dangerous” and “diverse discussion” (Eveland and Hively 2009). While the first describes political encounters that expose people only to discussion that conflicts with their views or characteristics, the second entails contexts in which a person encounters a mix of similar and dissimilar political views (Eveland and Hively 2009).

When exposure to political disagreement is seen as a matter of degree, measured on a continuous scale where exclusive exposure to similar and dissimilar views are the extremes, results

suggest that increased exposure to political disagreement significantly reduces the likelihood of turnout (Mutz 2002b, 2006; Pattie and Johnston 2009, but see Leighley 1990 for the opposite finding, i.e. that increased exposure to disagreement positively relates to voting). This finding suggests potential tensions between two normative ideals of democratic citizenship, namely that of an informed and that of a participative citizenry (Mutz 2006). While exposure to political disagreement in casual conversations carried out in personal social networks was shown to increase political knowledge and foster political tolerance, it appeared to hamper electoral mobilization.

However, when disagreement is seen not as a matter of degree but a discrete occurrence, results indicate that only political disagreement in “opposition networks” – social settings that expose people only to political views that run contrary to their own – delays the formation of voting preferences and depresses electoral participation (Nir 2011). Both ‘supportive’ – social settings in which people encounter only politically like-minded others – and ‘competitive’ or mixed networks – social instances in which people encounter a mix of political views, some of them in accordance and some in conflict with their own (Nir 2011) – help people making up their minds early in elections and increase their likelihood of voting.

Exposure to political disagreement, therefore, appears to delay the formation of political preferences and depress electoral participation only when people do not encounter any support for their political views (Nir 2011). This appears to be the result of social pressure, evoking Asch’s conclusions drawn in famous experimental studies that showed people would change their opinions on trivial issues in the presence of sheer opposition but stick to their position as long as their view was supported by at least one person in the group (Asch 1951).

The empirical study of the influences exerted by exposure to diverse vs. conflicting political views on electoral behavior appears to be thus warranted. Nevertheless, empirical evidence on this distinction is extremely scant and comes from studies that were conducted exclusively in the US (Eveland and Hively 2009; Nir 2011; Bello 2012). To date there is no study testing the effects of exposure to fully similar, fully dissimilar, and mixed political views in both strong and weak networks across various countries. Drawing on recent – though scant – evidence that exposure to disagreement is detrimental only in the absence of at least one person with whom respondents agree on political matters, I formulate the following hypothesis: (H1) Compared to those who encounter only dissimilar political views in their social networks, people who encounter a mix of similar and dissimilar political views are more likely to vote.

Given the lack of any comparative, cross-country research on the role of political similarity with social network members on individual turnout, I test whether the positive effect of exclusive exposure to similar political views that was observed in studies previously conducted in a small number of countries would hold in general, in both strong and weak social networks: (H2) People who are exposed only to similar political views in their social networks are more likely to vote.

A consistent finding of extant research is that mobilization by political conversation in social networks is more efficient when it originates in close or geographically proximate relationships (Faas and Schmitt-Beck 2010; Sinclair 2012). Among them, spouses are particularly influential (Zuckerman, Dasović, and Fitzgerald 2007; Schmitt-Beck and Mackenrodt 2009) and mobilizing efforts directed towards a person were shown to produce spillover effects in the household, thus reinforcing the claim that strong, intimate relationships are particularly conducive to political contagion (Nickerson 2008). These findings tally with Columbia’s school understanding of intimate relationships as main loci of political influence in elections (Lazarsfeld, Berelson, and Gaudet 1944; Berelson, Lazarsfeld, and

McPhee 1954). Experimental results strengthen these findings; political conversation is a strong mobilizing force in the presence of social intimacy (Klofstad 2011).

The finding of intimacy as a strong driving force of interpersonal influence was interpreted as indicative of social conformity rather than information gain being the major mechanism of social influence in politics (Sinclair 2012). This line of reasoning is strengthened by the finding of high political homophily between close relationships, very often taken as empirical evidence of reciprocal influences exerted between intimate peers. Being inherently social, this argument goes, people place a high value on maintaining harmonious relationships that were not originally formed based on political preferences. Embeddedness in close, intimate groups that are predominantly homogeneous in social structures, tastes, and activities pressures individuals whose political preferences depart from the dominant ones in the group (Sinclair 2012). This mechanism corresponds to what has been labeled as social cohesion or contagion and seen as the dominant theoretical paradigm of explaining social influence (Burt 1987).

This view was challenged though by a study that suggested that political disagreement is more likely to occur and last in intimate settings rather than in the presence of weak, functional relationships, such as neighbors, workmates, and general acquaintances. This is due to the fact that fear of social disapproval and rejection is greatly reduced in the presence of close others, a situation that relaxes the conversation and leads to more self-disclosure (Morey, Eveland, and Hutchens 2012). On the contrary, people might be more cautious to express disagreement with weak ties or secondary relationships, fearing social exclusion in the case of expressing views that deviate from the ones entertained by the majority of the group members.

Since both lines of argumentation pertaining to the influence exerted by disagreement with close peers are equally sound, I formulate a research question to explore potential differences in the relationship between exposure to political diversity in strong and weak social networks: (RQ1) Are there differences in the relationship between exposure to a diversity of similar and dissimilar political views and voting turnout in strong and weak social networks?

The moderating role of the length of democratic experience

Relationships hypothesized above are expected to be affected by macro-contextual features pertaining to political culture. In particular, I expect that differences in patterns of social and political communication to which inhabitants of old and new democracies have been exposed in their everyday social interactions would moderate the relationship between exposure to political similarity and diversity and individual turnout, both in the case of strong and weak social networks.

Comparative studies of interpersonal political communication have shown that compared to inhabitants of old democracies, citizens of countries emerging from a totalitarian or authoritarian past appear to be part of smaller, less diverse social networks, and be less likely to engage in political conversations with their peers (Bădescu 2003; Flap and Volker 2003; Howard 2003; Iglıc 2003; Iglıc and Fábregas 2007; Richardson and Beck 2007; Lup 2015). In addition to this, studies conducted in societies emerging relatively recent from an authoritarian past report people's 'reluctance to engage in discussion with those with whom they disagree', especially in countries 'that had experienced polarizing and traumatizing partisan conflict during and after a civil war', such as Spain (Beck and Gunther 2010).

The reluctance to engage in political conversations with holders of divergent political views in countries emerging from an undemocratic past was seen as a conscious effort made by citizens of newly democratized countries to focus on consensus building principles in politics. MacKuen (1990)

hypothesized that citizens of newly democratized countries would be more concerned with the destabilizing potential of encountering political disagreement in casual conversations with peers and therefore less likely to do so. This is due to the fact that these people have not grasped yet a fundamental aspect of democratic politics, which is the coexistence of disagreement on specific issues and policies, and agreement on basic principles of democratic politics. Citizens of countries with a longer democratic past might feel uncomfortable when encountering political disagreement in casual political conversations but, at the same time, aware that disagreement is about how to reach the goals on which almost everybody agrees and not about the goals themselves (MacKuen 1990).

Drawing on studies that evidence substantial differences in the ways people relate to the quotidian phenomenon of encountering political disagreement in countries with longer and more recent democratic experience, I expect that in newer democracies exposure to politically similar views will have a stronger mobilizing effect, while exposure to politically diverse views will play a stronger deterring role for electoral participation: (H3) The positive effect of exposure to political similarity is stronger in countries with a more recent democratic experience, and (H4) The positive effect of exposure to political diversity is stronger in countries with longer democratic experience.

Methods, data, and measures

To test these hypotheses, I use data collected in the Comparative National Elections Project (CNEP), a comparative, cross-country study that includes twenty-six national election surveys and has been conducted in eighteen countries since 1990. All three phases of the survey study were concerned with intermediation processes through which citizens receive information during electoral campaigns. The selection of the countries did not follow a random procedure and thus the result is a convenience sample. However, the countries are quite diverse with regard to their histories, institutions, and political cultures and this makes the study a relevant source for testing the effect of social networks on individual turnout in a comparative perspective.

To my knowledge, CNEP is the largest available data set to include detailed information about features of social networks and electoral behavior across a wide range of countries from South America, Southern, Eastern and Western Europe, East Asia, and the US. While a few of them have a long democratic history, many have a more recent democratic experience, or are not yet fully democratized. The sampling procedures were different and included simple and multi-stage stratified random samples. Data was collected through either face-to-face or phone interviews.

Individual turnout. The response variable in my analysis is individual turnout. It is a dichotomous measure recording respondents' self-declared participation in the most recent national elections (voted).

Social networks. Most of the previous research on the social underpinnings of political behavior has looked at dyadic relationships as the primary loci of social influences in politics (Huckfeldt and Sprague 1995). In my study I analyze social networks as unitary structures whose logic of influence differs from the one that stems from dyadic relations. This understanding is similar to what Ikeda (2010) calls 'interpersonal political environment (IPE)'. Social networks define environments that are more than the sum of the dyadic relationships that form them. They create constraints and opportunities that surpass those emerging from dyadic social interactions. For example, the demobilizing effect of exposure to political disagreement in a dyadic relationship might be reduced if the network in which the person is embedded contains people with similar political views.

Measures of strong social networks. Information about strong social networks comes from questions asking respondents about their habits of discussing politics with their spouse/partner and

two people with whom they usually discuss important matters. Measures of strong social networks were collected in Argentina (2007), Bulgaria (1996), Chile (1993), Greece (1996), Hungary (2006), Mexico (2006), Mozambique (2004), South Africa (2004), Spain (1993), Taiwan (2004), and the US (2004).

The size of the strong discussion network ('size strong') is a count of the people from the core network with whom respondents declared discussing politics. It takes values from 0 to 3.

Frequency of political discussion in strong social networks ('strong talk') is the sum of three indicators that measure how frequently respondents discuss politics with their spouse/partner and two important other people. The measures recording frequency of talk for each of the three dyads range from 0 indicating that the two people have never talked politics to 3 meaning that they have talked often. 'Strong talk' takes values from 0 to 9.

To compute indicators of the level of diversity of political encounters in strong social networks I used questions asking respondents how often they agreed with their spouse and two important others when discussing politics during the most recent electoral campaign. The measures range from 0 indicating that the two have never agreed to 3 meaning that they very often have agreed. For each discussion partner I computed three dichotomous indicators that separate between instances of exclusive agreement, exclusive disagreement, and cases of exposure to both agreement and disagreement in conversations with strong network members. I then summed up these categories across the three discussion partners and created three indicators of the political composition of strong networks. 'Strong similarity' takes values from 0 to 3 and counts the number of core network members with whom respondents always agree when discussing politics. 'Strong dissimilarity' takes values from 0 to 3 and counts the number of core network members with whom respondents always disagree when discussing politics. Finally, 'strong diversity' records those cases in which respondents are embedded in politically diverse conversational settings. The variable goes from 0 to 3.

For example, if a respondent who reports discussing politics with her spouse and two important others declares that she always agrees with each of them, strong similarity takes the value 3 and both strong dissimilarity and diversity value 0. In case a respondent who reports discussing politics with her spouse and two important others declares that she always agrees with the spouse and experience a mix of agreement and disagreement with the two important others, strong similarity takes the value 1, strong dissimilarity 0, and strong diversity 2.

Measures of weak social networks. Information about weak social networks comes from questions asking respondents about their habits of engaging in political conversations with their workmates and neighbors. Although some authors have included conversations with friends in computing measures of weak networks, I opted for a very conservative measure with the intention of clearly discriminating between the two types of social interactions, which I see embodying different logics of social interaction.

Data about weak social networks comes from a partly different set of countries compared to the ones that included information about strong social networks, namely Argentina (2007), Chile (1993), Hungary (1998), Mexico (2006), Mozambique (2004), South Africa (2004), Taiwan (2004), US (2004), and Uruguay (1994).

To facilitate the comparison of the effects exerted by political conversation carried out within the two types of social networks, these indicators mirror the ones computed for measuring the political composition of strong social networks.

The size of weak social networks ('size weak') is a count of the groups with whom respondents report discussing politics. It takes values from 0 to 2.

Frequency of political discussion in weak social networks ('weak talk') is the sum of two indicators that record respondents' self-declared frequency of political talk during the most recent electoral campaign in two social settings, namely with workmates and with neighbors. Each of these variables ranges from 0 indicating that respondents have never talked politics in that setting to 3 meaning that they talked often. 'Weak talk' takes values from 0 to 6.

Three indicators of the composition of weak networks are computed. They draw on questions asking respondents whether, when discussing politics with workmates and neighbors they always agree, always disagree, or discussions entail a mix of agreeable and disagreeable political views. Based on this data I computed a set of six dichotomous variables that separate instances in which respondents and discussants always agree, always disagree, and those in which they encounter a mix of political views in conversations with neighbors and workmates, respectively. I then summed up these variables across the two weak social networks and created three indicators. Exclusive exposure to political agreement in conversations that take place in weak networks ('weak similarity') is an index of the settings where respondents encounter – or at least perceive it so – only similar political views. 'Weak dissimilarity' counts the number of settings where respondents encounter only opposing political views and 'weak diversity' indicates the number of settings in which respondents encounter both agreement and disagreement. Each of these three measures takes values from 0 to 2.

Control variables. To account for the possibility that variation in both measures of social networks and individual turnout are influenced by some exogeneous factors I control for variables that might be related to both of them. These are socio demographics, namely age, gender, and education, and measures of cognitive involvement with politics, namely consumption of political news in various media, political interest, and strength of partisanship.

Age is a variable measuring respondents' self-declared age. Education is a 7-point variable recording respondents' self-declared highest educational attainment. Gender (female) is a dichotomous variable where women are coded 1 and men 0.

Partisanship is a 4-point variable recording respondents' self-declared strength of partisan identification. Media attentiveness (media) measures frequency of following political news during the most recent electoral campaign in five types of media, namely magazines, newspapers, radio, and TV. Each of these variables take values from 0, meaning the respondent has never followed that medium, to 4, meaning the respondent very often has done it. The final measure takes values from 0 to 20, with higher scores indicating increased level of media attentiveness. Political interest sums two measures recording respondents' self-declared level of interest in politics, in general, and in the events of the most recent electoral campaign, in particular. General political interest is measured on a 4-point scale (0 to 3) and interest in the most recent electoral campaign is measured on a 5-point scale (0 to 4). The resulting measure (political interest) takes values from 0 to 7, with higher scores indicating an increased interest in politics.

Length of democratic experience. Democratic experience ('democracy') measures for how long a country has been a democracy, i.e. taking as the reference point the first free and fair elections held in the country.

Results

Given the multilevel nature of my data, – individuals in the surveys are nested in countries – I employ hierarchical analysis to test the effects that specific features of social networks have on voting across various countries, and to estimate unbiased coefficients and standard errors (Steenbergen and Jones 2002; Gelman & Hill 2007). Specifically, I conduct mixed effects logistic regression analysis, in which

the intercept and the effects of political similarity and diversity are specified as random. This is due to the fact that I assume that there is significant between-group variability on the dependent variable and I expect that the effects of exposure to politically similar and diverse views on voting vary across countries that differ in their length of democratic experience among other things.

Table 1. Intimate social networks and individual turnout (logistic estimates with s.e. in parentheses).

	Model 1		Model 2	
<i>Fixed effects</i>				
<i>Level 1 variables</i>				
Constant	-0.83 ***	(.23)	0.53	(.51)
Age	0.02 ***	(.00)	0.02 ***	(.00)
Education	0.05 *	(.02)	0.05 *	(.02)
Female	0.10	(.06)	0.10	(.06)
Core size	-0.07	(.08)	-0.08	(.08)
Core talk	0.06 *	(.03)	0.06 *	(.03)
Core similarity	0.26 **	(.09)	0.05	(.20)
Core diversity	0.08	(.08)	-0.25	(.14)
Partisanship	0.33 ***	(.03)	0.33 ***	(.03)
Political interest	0.21 ***	(.02)	0.21 ***	(.02)
Media	0.03 ***	(.01)	0.03 **	(.01)
<i>Level 2 variables</i>				
Democracy			-0.51 **	(.18)
<i>Cross-level interactions</i>				
Core similarity x Democracy			0.08	(.07)
Core diversity x Democracy			0.12 *	(.04)
<i>Random effects</i>				
Intercept	0.64	(.15)	0.52	(.13)
Core similarity	0.18	(.06)	0.17	(.06)
Core diversity	0.10	(.05)	0.07	(.06)
-2 Log likelihood	4176		4170	
No of cases level 1	11012		11012	
No of cases level 2	11		11	

Core social networks and voting. Table 1 reports the results of estimating mixed effects logistic regression models with individual turnout as response variable and measures of strong social networks as explanatory variables. Results indicate that compared to people who encounter only dissimilar political views, those who are exposed exclusively to similar political views in their conversations with strong network members are more likely to vote. This brings support to hypothesis H2.

More frequent political discussion with strong network members increases the likelihood of voting. The effect of political diversity does not reach a conventional level of statistical significance (hypothesis H1), although the sign is in the expected direction, i.e. positive. Therefore, the finding that exposure to political diversity boosts voting whereas experience of political dissimilarity depresses it does not appear to hold outside the American context in which it was evidenced (Nir 2011) and neither

does the expectation that exposure to diversity in strong networks would generate electoral mobilization.

The second column of Table 1 presents the results of testing hypotheses H3 and H4, pertaining to differences in the effect of exposure to political similarity and diversity as a function of the length of democratic experience of the country. Results bring support to hypothesis H4, but not to H3. In countries with longer democratic experience, exposure to diverse political views in one's strong network of political discussants positively affects her likelihood of casting a ballot. This confirms the expectations formulated by scholars such as MacKuen (1990) that inhabitants of countries with longer democratic experiences are used with the inherent tensions of democratic politics and do not fear their destabilizing potential. Therefore, they benefit from exposure to political views that contradict their own inasmuch as this happens in the safe space of intimate relationships, where disagreement can be further discussed and pondered without fearing social disapproval and exclusion. The positive effect of exposure to political similarity, though, does not appear to be affected by the length of democratic experience of a country.

Table 2. Generic social networks and individual turnout (logistic estimates with s.e. in parentheses).

	Model 1		Model 2	
<i>Fixed effects</i>				
<i>Level 1 variables</i>				
Constant	-0.98 **	(.23)	0.53	(.51)
Age	0.03 ***	(.00)	0.03 ***	(.00)
Education	0.16 ***	(.02)	0.16 ***	(.02)
Female	0.16 *	(.06)	0.16 *	(.06)
Functional network size	-0.19 *	(.08)	-0.18	(.08)
Functional talk	0.08	(.03)	0.08	(.03)
Functional similarity	0.36 **	(.09)	0.13	(.20)
Functional diversity	0.16	(.08)	-0.09	(.14)
Partisanship	0.26 ***	(.03)	0.26 ***	(.03)
Political interest	0.23 ***	(.02)	0.23 ***	(.02)
Media	0.04 ***	(.01)	0.04 ***	(.01)
<i>Level 2 variables</i>				
Democracy			-0.52 **	(.16)
<i>Cross-level interactions</i>				
Functional similarity x Democracy			0.08	(.09)
Functional diversity x Democracy			0.07	(.05)
<i>Random effects</i>				
Intercept	0.73	(.18)	0.49	(.13)
Functional similarity	0.21	(.12)	0.22	(.12)
Functional diversity	0.00	(.12)	0.00	(.09)
-2 Log likelihood	2655		2651	
No of cases level 1	7081		7081	
No of cases level 2	9		9	

Weak social networks and voting. Table 2 reports the results of estimating mixed effects logistic regression models with individual turnout as response variable and measures of weak social networks as explanatory variables. Results indicate that as in the case of political similarity in strong networks, exclusive exposure to similar political views in weak social networks increases the likelihood of voting in elections. There appears to be strong support for the expectation formulated by hypothesis H2. The effect of exposure to political diversity in weak networks, though, does not reach a conventional level of statistical significance.

The second column of Table 2 presents the results of testing the hypotheses pertaining to the moderating influence of length of democratic experience of countries on the effect that weak social networks have on individual turnout. They indicate that the positive effect of encountering political similarity in weak networks is not enhanced in countries with a recent undemocratic past.

Discussion

Taking stock of the results of the analysis carried out in this paper indicates three major conclusions.

Firstly, my analysis provided evidence for a general positive effect of exposure to political similarity on individual turnout. This confirms what has been previously observed in individual country analysis but never tested in a comparative, cross-country research.

Secondly, my research did not find evidence in support of the claim that compared to the detrimental effect of exclusive exposure to dissimilar political views, the experience of a mix of similar and dissimilar views in casual conversations with peers leads to electoral mobilization. This finding does not appear to hold on a larger scale and outside the American context in which it was observed (Nir 2011).

Thirdly and closely related to the previous one, the beneficial role of exposure to diverse political views envisaged by scholars of deliberative democracy appears to hold under two circumstances. Specifically, exposure to diverse political views positively affects individual turnout when occurring among members of strong social networks and in countries with a longer democratic past.

This latter conclusion brings evidence in support of the claim that strong, core social settings are safer loci for revealing one's genuine preferences and engaging in real political debates without fearing social disapproval and exclusion. Absent social constraints, exposure to divergent political views enlarges one's political understanding and makes her more aware of her own position and views, thus reducing the uncertainties related to vote choice. Nevertheless, this seems to hold only in countries with a longer democratic past, where people have learnt to live with the inherent tensions of democratic politics and therefore do not fear the destabilizing character of political disagreement.

Before discussing the relevance of these findings, a few caveats should be noticed. First of all, the small number of countries included in the hierarchical analysis raises the issue of the validity of the estimates. Stegmueller (2013) indicated that in hierarchical analysis where the number of cases at the second level is small, random coefficients are not biased, but the confidence intervals are too lenient, presenting anticonservative tests. Fixed effects, on the other hand, are not affected, while a rather serious problem is posed by the estimation of cross-interaction effects.

Second, the second level cases are not randomly chosen, and this limits my ability to draw general conclusions. However, the countries are quite different and therefore, although they might not be representative of the whole universe of countries, their diversity makes possible to see the findings as indicative of the relationships between social networks and political engagement in a broader perspective.

Finally, an important limitation of this study is that the cross-sectional data that I employ makes impossible an examination of the direction of these effects. In these analyses I assumed that the classical direction of influence, i.e. from political discussion to political engagement, applies. Empirical research that used panel data provides evidence with regard to effects flowing from political discussion to electoral participation (Toka 2010). Moreover, the results of experimental studies lend strong empirical support to the claim that political discussion advances civic participation (Klofstad 2011).

What is the relevance of these findings? First of all, they bring empirical support to the claim that people do not make their political decisions in isolation; the web of the social interactions in which they are enmeshed significantly affects their decision to cast a vote. This suggests that failure to include micro social contexts among explanatory variables in models of individual turnout would result in biased estimates of other predictors and erroneous conclusions with regard to the antecedents of individual political engagement. Recent studies suggest that indicators of social connectivity are not a mere addition to explicans of voting behavior; they also elucidate the link between classical predictors of political engagement, such as education, for example, and voting (Rolfe 2012).

Second, these findings suggest that political discussion in micro social environments functions as a link between private and public spheres. When two friends engage in a political conversation while sipping their coffees, their private relationship opens to the public sphere. They might agree or disagree, but when accepting to discuss political issues, they engage in a process that might have far reaching consequences for their political decisions. Their discussion is no longer one between two private egos but one in which two people negotiate their understanding of citizenship. They can do this while discussing issues as salient as the most recent comments of the electoral candidates on TV or their take on some specific healthcare policy.

Last but not least, these findings suggest that the study of the role of political discussion carried out in different social networks for individual political behavior is worth further investigation. The results of this analysis indicated that, in general, exposure to politically congenial social settings is a mighty mobilizing force. Moreover, in countries with a longer democratic experience, where people do not perceive disagreement as a destabilizing factor, exposure to a mix of political views in conversations carried out in more laidback social environments, among close, intimate others appears to lead to electoral mobilization. Is this due to the fact that in intimate settings, the acknowledgment of political disagreement is followed up by genuine debates since people care about understanding why their significant others diverge on this or that issue? Although such a scenario would fall short of ideal situations in which citizens engage in political conversations with less intimate others in public places, strong social networks – inasmuch as they do not expose people exclusively to similar political views – might provide better settings for discussions that closely approximate the ideal of deliberation, at least for lay citizens.

Such an interpretation is supported by the finding that the motivation behind engaging in political conversations appears to be different in the case of what I labeled here as strong and weak social interactions. ‘Political conversations with neighbors and coworkers tend to be motivated primarily by a desire to pass the time or to stimulate an interesting debate. In contrast, individuals are not motivated to try to “teach” something to these individuals. Political conversations with romantic partners and relatives are more likely to be motivated by efforts to form an opinion, and to a lesser extent they are more likely to have a “teaching” motivation than for other relationship types’ (Eveland, Morey, and Hutchens 2011).

References

- Bădescu, G. (2003). Social trust and democratization in the post-communist societies. In G. Bădescu, & E. Uslaner (Eds.), *Social Capital and Transition to Democracy* (pp. 208-238). London: Routledge.
- Beck, P. A., & Gunther, R. (2010). *Global Patterns of Political Intermediation*. Paper presented at the conference of the Comparative National Election Project. July 22-24, Shanghai, China.
- Bello, J. 2012. The Dark Side of Disagreement? Revisiting the Effect of Disagreement on Political Participation. *Electoral Studies*, 31(4), 782-795.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electstud.2012.06.004>
- Berelson, B. R., Lazarsfeld, P. F., & McPhee, W. N. (1954). *Voting: A Study of Opinion Formation in a Presidential Campaign*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Bryk, A. S., & Raudenbush, S. W. (1992). *Hierarchical linear models*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Burt, R. S. (1987). Social contagion and innovation: Cohesion versus structural equivalence. *American Journal of Sociology*, 92(6), 1287-1335. <https://doi.org/10.1086/228667>
- Christakis, N. A., & Fowler, J. H. (2009). *Connected: The Surprising Power of Our Social Networks and How They Shape Our Lives*. New York: Little, Brown and Company.
- Eveland, W. P., Song, H., & Beck, P.A. (2015). Cultural Variations in the Relationships Among Network Political Agreement, Political Discussion Frequency, and Voting Turnout. *International Journal of Public Opinion Research*, 27(4), 461-480. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ijpor/edv007>
- Eveland, W. P., Morey, A. C., & Hutchens, M. J. (2011). Beyond deliberation: New directions for the study of informal political conversation from a communication perspective. *Journal of Communication*, 61(6), 1082-1103. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2011.01598.x>
- Eveland, W.P., & Hutchens, M. J. (2009). Political discussion frequency, network size, and „heterogeneity“ of discussion as predictors of political knowledge and participation. *Journal of Communication*, 59(2), 205-224. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2009.01412.x>
- Faas, T., & Schmitt-Beck, R. (2010). Voters' Political Conversations During the 2005 German Parliamentary Election Campaign. In M. R. Wolf, L. Morales, & K. Ikeda (Eds.), *Political Discussion in Modern Democracies: a comparative perspective* (pp. 99-116). Routledge: London.
- Fishkin, J. S. (1991). *Democracy and Deliberation: New directions for democratic reform*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Flap, H., & Volker, B. (2003). Communist Societies, the velvet revolution, and weak ties: The case of East Germany. In G. Bădescu, & E. Uslaner (Eds.), *Social Capital and Transition to Democracy* (pp. 28-45). London: Routledge.
- Fowler, J. (2005). Turnout in a Small World. In A. S. Zuckerman (Ed.), *The Social Logic of Politics: Personal Networks as Contexts for Political Behavior* (pp. 269-187). Philadelphia: Temple University Press.
- Gelman, A., & Hill, J. (2007). *Data Analysis Using Regression and Multilevel/Hierarchical Models*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Granovetter, M. (1973). The Strength of Weak Ties. *American Journal of Sociology*, 78(6), 1360-1380.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/225469>
- Howard, M. M. (2003). *The Weakness of Civil Society in Post-Communist Europe*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Huckfeldt, R., & Sprague, J. (1995). *Citizens, Politics and Social Communication: Information and influence in an election campaign*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- Iglic, H., Fabregas, J. F. (2007). Social networks. In A. Westholm, J. R. Montero, & J. W. van Deth (Eds.), *Citizenship and Involvement in European Democracies: a comparative analysis* (pp. 188-217). London: Routledge.
- Iglic, H. (2003). Trust networks and democratic transition: Yugoslavia in the mid-1980s. In G. Bădescu, & E. Uslaner (Eds.), *Social Capital and Transition to Democracy*. London: Routledge.
- Ikeda, K. (2010). Social networks, voting and campaign participation in Japan: the interpersonal political environment and the autonomous dimension of social networks. In M. R. Wolf, L. Morales, & K. Ikeda (Eds.), *Political Discussion in Modern Democracies: a comparative perspective* (pp. 162-182). Routledge: London.
- Klofstad, C. A. (2011). *Civic Talk: Peers, Politics and the Future of Democracy*. Philadelphia: Temple University Press.
- Knoke, D. (1990). *Political Networks. The Structural Perspective*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Lazarsfeld, P. F., Berelson, B., & Gaudet, H. (1944). *The People's Choice: How the Voter Makes Up His Mind in a Presidential Campaign*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Leighley, J. E. (1990). Social Interaction and Contextual Influences on Political Participation. *American Politics Quarterly*, 18(4), 459-475. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1532673X9001800404>
- Marsden, P. V. (1987). Core discussion networks of Americans. *American Sociological Review*, 52(1), 122-131. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2095397>
- MacKuen, M. B. (1990). Speaking of Politics: Individual Conversational Choice, Public Opinion, and the Prospects for Deliberative Democracy. In J. A. Ferejohn, & J. Kuklinski (Eds.), *Information and Democratic Processes* (pp. 55-59). Urbana: University of Illinois Press.
- Morales, L. (2010). Getting a single message? The impact of homogeneous political communication contexts in Spain in a comparative perspective. In M. R. Wolf, L. Morales, & K. Ikeda (Eds.), *Political Discussion in Modern Democracies: a comparative perspective* (pp. 201-222). Routledge: London.
- Morey, A. C., Eveland, W. P., & Hutchens, M. J. (2012). The "Who" Matters: Types of Interpersonal Relationships and Avoidance of Political Disagreement. *Political Communication*, 29(1): 86-103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10584609.2011.641070>
- Mutz, D. C., & Mondak, J. (2006). The Workplace as a Context for Cross-Cutting Political Discourse. *Journal of Politics*, 68(1), 140-155. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2508.2006.00376.x>
- Mutz, D. C. (2006). *Hearing the Other Side: Deliberative Versus Participatory Democracy*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Mutz, D. C. (2002a). Cross-Cutting Social Networks: Testing Democratic Theory in Practice. *American Political Science Review* 96(1), 111-126. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003055402004264>
- Mutz, D. C. (2002b). The Consequences of Cross-Cutting Networks for Political Participation. *American Journal of Political Science*, 46(4), 838-855. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3088437>
- Nickerson, D. W. (2008). Is Voting Contagious? Evidence from Two Field Experiments. *American Political Science Review*, 102(1), 49-57. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003055408080039>
- Nir, L. (2011). Disagreement and Opposition in Social Networks: Does Disagreement Discourage Turnout? *Political Studies*, 59(3), 674-692. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9248.2010.00873.x>
- Nir, L. (2005). Ambivalent Social Networks and Their Consequences for Participation. *International Journal of Public Opinion Research*, 17(4), 422-442. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ijpor/edh069>
- Pattie, C., & Johnston, R. (2009). Conversation, Disagreement and Political Participation. *Political Behavior*, 31(2): 261-285. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11109-008-9071-z>

- Putnam, R. D. (2000). *Bowling alone: The collapse and revival of American community*. New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Rolfe, M. (2012). *Voter Turnout: A Social Theory of Political Participation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Richardson, B., & Beck, P. A. (2007). The Flow of Political Information: Personal Discussants, the Media, and Parties. In R. Gunther, H. J. Puhle, & J. R. Montero (Eds.), *Democracy, Intermediation, and Voting on Four Continents* (pp. 183-207). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Schmitt-Beck, R., & Mackenrodt, C.. (2010). Social Networks and Mass Media as Mobilizers and Demobilizers: A Study of Turnout at a German Local Election. *Electoral Studies*, 29(3): 392-404. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electstud.2010.03.011>
- Schmitt-Beck, R. (2008). Interpersonal Communication. In C. Holtz-Bacha, and L. L. Kaid (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Political Communication* (pp. 341-350). Los Angeles: Sage.
- Sinclair, B. (2012). *The Social Citizen. Peer Networks and Political Behavior*. Chicago/London: University of Chicago Press.
- Steenbergen, M., & Brdford, S. J. (2002). Modeling Multilevel Data Structures. *American Journal of Political Science*, 46(1), 218-237. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3088424>
- Stegmueller, D. (2013). How Many Countries for Multilevel Modeling? A Comparison of Frequentist and Bayesian Approaches. *American Journal of Political Science*, 57(3), 748-761. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajps.12001>
- Toka, G. (2010). The impact of everyday political talk on involvement, knowledge and informed voting. In M. R. Wolf, L. Morales, & K. Ikeda (Eds.), *Political Discussion in Modern Democracies: a comparative perspective* (pp. 162-182). London: Routledge.
- Volker, B., & Flap, H. (2001). Weak ties as a liability: the case of East Germany. *Rationality and Society*, 13(4), 397-428. <https://doi.org/10.1177/104346301013004001>
- Zuckerman, A., Dasović, J., & Fitzgerald, J. (2007). *Partisan Families: The Social Logic of Bounded Partisanship in Germany and Britain*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.